

IMPACT STUDY OF VARIOUS PHARMACEUTICAL PROMOTIONAL PRACTICES ON INDIAN DOCTOR'S PRESCRIPTION BEHAVIOR

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Abstract - Purpose: *This paper seeks to identify the impact of various pharmaceutical promotional tools on the prescription behaviour of doctors. Design/methodology/approach:* *To analyse, 100 self-administered structured questionnaires were collected from doctors practicing in different specialties like General practitioner, Physician, Gynecologist, Pediatrician, and Dentist. The hypothesis was developed based on various promotional activities like detailing of a medical representative, continuing medical education, medical camps, and customer relationship management and its impact on doctor's prescription behaviour. Findings:* *The finding of the research paper shows that various promotional activities like detailing of a medical representative, continuing medical education, medical camps, and customer relationship management have impact on the prescription behaviour of doctors but at varying rates. Role of customer relationship management is crucial followed by medical representative detailing, medical camp & continuous medical education, which have significant positive impact on the doctor's prescription choice. Practical implications:* *The results could help pharmaceutical companies to develop a range of promotional tools for their products which help them to generate maximum return on investment. The result also improve the understanding of drug control authorities and health policymakers, in controlling unethical medical practices by doctors. Originality/value:* *This paper reports an original empirical study on the prescription behaviour of healthcare practitioners in the context of promotional tools.*

Keywords: *Pharmaceutical promotion; prescribing behaviour; general practitioner; prescription*

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Ruining title: *Pharma promotion & impact on doctor's prescription*

INTRODUCTION

India enjoys an important position in the global pharmaceuticals market. Being the largest supplier of generic drugs worldwide, its pharmaceutical industry provides more than 50 percent of the global vaccine requirement, 40 percent of general pharmaceutical needs in the United States and 25 percent of all vaccines in the UK (1). India also has a large pool of scientists and engineers with the potential to move the industry forward and at the highest level. The Indian pharmaceutical market is comparable with the global market as it ranked 3rd & 13th in terms of volume and value respectively. In 2018, the Indian market was around 18.12 billion USD in absolute value with growth of 9.4% year on year, out of it branded generics have 90% share, rest 10% share is taken by generic medicines (1) (2). Government, NGOs & pharmaceutical companies are trying to create awareness among the population about various disease conditions with different set of objectives; but thereby spending on medicines is expected to grow by 9-12% over the next five years, compelling India to rank among the top 10 countries in terms of medicinal

spending (1). Next generation biotherapeutics, artificial intelligence, cellular programming, nanotechnology, genetics, prescription digital therapeutics are just few of the emerging trends for the pharmaceutical market (3) (4) (5). The newer technologies and therapies add quality of life to patients but come with great cost. Health insurance may decrease the cost burden to patients but Indian patients do not usually purchase health insurance. Government of India has an initiative called Ayushman Bharat Yojna which provides free health care services to patients below poverty line. However, such emerging therapies will still be out of the reach of most Indian patients except elite population of metropolitan areas. To reduce the health care costs the government has promoted generic drugs but Indian patients still continue to prefer brand prescription. This encourages pharmaceutical companies to increase spending on various promotional practices. Changing government policies, constant pricing pressure & generic drugs are the challenging issues for pharmaceutical companies (6).

As per the IMS prescription report 2019, in India 345305 doctors generate 2.45 billion prescriptions every year. The highest prescriptions are generated by general practitioners, almost 985 million which contributes 39% of total prescriptions generated in country. The dentist is the 2nd biggest specialty with almost 274 million prescription followed by consultant physicians with 209 million prescriptions. Top 5 specialties contributes almost 73% of prescriptions [Table 1] (7).

Table 1: No of doctors in India as per their specialty and no of prescriptions generated every year by each specialty

Specialty	No of Doctors	Total Prescriptions	% Contribution
Total	3,45,305	2,54,64,88,300	100
General Practitioner	1,24,649	98,55,07,226	39
Dentist	44,789	27,39,54,572	11
Cons. Physician	26,342	20,90,45,443	8
Gynaecologist	28,563	19,73,16,096	8
Paediatrician	20,361	19,69,94,358	8
Orthopaedics	15,126	10,23,82,366	4
Gen. Surgeon	13,341	9,19,87,908	4
Ophthalmologist	13,101	8,90,95,450	3
ENT Specialist	9,575	7,66,55,204	3
Cardiologist	8,629	6,05,50,614	2

After patent expiry, Indian pharmaceuticals companies promote generic drug with own brand name as a branded generics. In such condition, any company can manufacture drug and promote their brand in front of the doctor, which make pharmaceutical market very competitive in nature. Customer is not the client, it's another aspect of pharmaceutical marketing. Therefore, doctors are a major factor in the sale of medicines because they specify the instructions to be used by patients. Due to this, it's very important for pharmaceutical companies to understand that how to influence doctor's prescribing behavior by using different types of marketing promotional tools. Thus, most pharmaceutical companies spend more than a third of their sales revenue on promotional tools, almost twice as much as they spend on R&D, in an effort to maintain and expand their market share (8).

Figures 1: Expenditure spread of large pharmaceutical companies (9)

In the past 20 years, doctor and pharmaceutical industry relationships have received considerable attention and many studies have been published to establish the relationship between different tools used by the pharmaceutical company to greet doctors (10).

Pharmaceutical companies try to convince their target audience like doctors for prescription products and patients for over the counter products that their product has better efficacy. To convince doctors for prescribe their brands, companies apply marketing strategies like sample packs, gifting, sponsorship for conferences, etc. Observing recent market dynamics, it is important to evaluate the impact of various promotional activities done by pharmaceutical companies on doctor's prescription behaviour. This research is an effort to understand various pharmaceutical promotional activities influencing doctors and their impact on their prescription behaviour.

Pharmaceutical companies employ medical representatives (MRs) and provide them a defined areas to meet with physicians, chemists and stockists. MRs meet doctors to influence their prescription pattern in favor of their brands (11). Detailing, is the most important task that a medical representative has to perform. Effective detailing with the help of a visual aid is the most important promotional tool to increase prescription generation. Continues medical education (CME) is the most preferred tool used by the pharmaceutical companies to gain confidence of doctor over promoted molecule and thereby brand (12). Free medical checkup camp is a patient centric activity organized by pharmaceutical companies to attract more number of patients at doctor's step. As it helps doctor to increase their patient pool, majority of doctors allow pharmaceutical companies to organize free medical camps. Customer relationship management is a crucial marketing tool for any business to maintain their clientele base. Pharmaceutical companies use many tools to engage doctors but detailing by MR, CME, medical camp and CRM are more frequently used tools & thereby gain the attention of researchers to study the impact of these tools on doctor's prescribing behavior.

PROBLEM STATEMENT & OBJECTIVE

Many new pharmaceutical companies have entered the Indian pharmaceutical market with their product range. Many combinations and acquisitions are possible. Notably, the marketing strategy of pharmaceutical companies has also changed with the passage of time. Therefore, it is important to look at the changes that occur in the marketing of prescription-based drugs. In this intense competition, pharmaceutical companies use their best marketing minds to convert doctors for their brand. Many studies narrated the impact of different pharmaceutical promotional tools and their impact on health care professional's prescribing behaviour, but very few of them are on Indian market. Indian pharmaceutical market is different in terms of their product range. Indian pharmaceutical market is dominated by branded generic products rather than innovative / research products.

The objective of this study is to identify the impact of pharmaceutical promotional tools on doctor's prescribing behaviour in Indian market which is majorly driven by me too kind of branded generic

products. The selection of appropriate activity, is equally important to establish brand in healthcare professional's mind.

METHOD

This study is quantitative in nature. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. Data was collected using primary data set through the distribution of questionnaire. The survey relates doctors of five different specialties: General Practitioner, Consulting Physician, Dentist, Paediatrician and Gynaecologist. These specialities are selected because they cover 70% of doctors and 72% of prescription. Survey was conducted in metro city of Gujarat, Ahmedabad. According to Levin et al and Kothari et al a good sample is one that meets the requirements of excellence, representation and trust (13) (14). As per the Ahmedabad medical association, total 7000 doctors are registered in Ahmedabad city, which is considered as a population (N). With confidence level of 95% & margin of error 0.1, value of sample calculated as 117. Stratified Random Sampling was chosen for the study (15). At first doctors were bifurcated in 5 different subgroups according to their speciality. A total of 120 doctors were selected randomly from subgroups as a sample of the study. Structured questionnaire was distributed among selected doctors contacted through personal visits or email or google forms. 107 responses received, out of them unfilled or partially submitted or unappropriated questionnaire were removed, 100 responses were appropriate for data analysis. The data was analysed with the help of the statistical package SPSS 22.

STUDY MODEL AND HYPOTHESIS

The proposed theoretical research model has been developed based on a literature review and explores the research objectives as seen above. Figure 2 displays the proposed relationship between the variables of the study.

Figure 2. Research model

The hypothesis is pharmaceutical promotional tools like detailing of medical representative, continuous medical education, medical camps and customer relationship management have positive impact on doctor's prescription behaviour. This research is an exploratory, quantitative, cross-sectional research.

RESULTS

A total of 100 doctors from various practicing specialties taken as a sample for this study, the profile of the respondents are, General Practitioner and Dentist together represent 51% of the sample, followed by Consulting Physician, Paediatrician and Gynaecologist all together 49% of the sample. All the doctors are showing interest in promotional activities led by the pharmaceutical companies. About 78% of the doctors prefer patient oriented activities and rest of the 22% prefer practice oriented activities.

Table 2: Sample Profile

Specialty	No of responses
General Practitioner	26
Consulting Physician	18
Dentist	25
Paediatrician	18
Gynaecologist	13
Total	100

Kind of activity preferred by respondent	No of responses
Patient oriented	78
Practice oriented	22
Total	100

Pharmaceutical promotional activities can be divided in two different categories, patient oriented and practice oriented. Patient oriented activity defined as an activity which helps patient to understand a disease condition or helps patient for better treatment like patient education videos, dos and don'ts of disease etc. Such kind of activity helps doctor to oblige their patient pool; in return it helps to get prescription support from doctor for pharmaceutical company. Practice oriented activity helps doctor to sharpen their expertise for improve clinical experience like CMEs, workshops, conferences etc.

Table 3: Practice and patient profile of sample

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
How long you are practicing?	1.00	40.00	9.69	6.66
How many average patients per day	4.00	50.00	19.10	11.17

The doctors in the sample have the lowest work experience of 1 year practicing and as high as 40 years, with an average time of practicing 9 years with a deviation of 6 years. The treatment for average patients per day is as low as 4 to a maximum of 50 patients per day, with an average patients 19 per day.

Convergent Validity and Reliability

The questionnaire adopted in this study uses a 7 point scale on which the measurements are developed and tested for validity by using the review of literature and expert opinion. According to Sekaran and Roger et al (16), it is important to make sure that the instrument developed to measure a particular concept is accurately measuring the variable and is actually measuring the concept that it is supposed to measure in the research. Indeed, reliability analysis is related to the assessment of the degree of consistency between multiple measurements of a variable, whereas validity analysis refers to the degree to which a scale or set of measures accurately represents the construct (17).

The reliability of the instrument was measured by the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Further, some scholars e.g. Bagozzi et al (18) suggested that the values of all indicators or dimensional scales should be above the recommended value of 0.60. From the table 3.1 the reliability analysis of all the constructs indicates high reliability as it is above 0.6, which is a good signal.

Validity of tool is measured by Average variance explained (AVE) which should be greater than 0.5 according to Hair et al (19). In the table 3.1 the Average variance explained (AVE) of all the construct is greater than 0.5 which confirms the validity of tool.

Table 4: **Reliability and Validity Statistics**

Construct	Cronbach's alpha	CR	AVE
Detailing of medical representative	0.756	0.735	0.601
Continues Medical Education	0.766	0.754	0.586
Medical camp	0.809	0.788	0.629
Customer relationship management	0.794	0.773	0.679

The results show that composite reliability (CR) for all the constructs are above the threshold value of 0.7, thus confirm the validity of the questionnaire instruments.

Data Variables and Measurement:

Table 5: Mean summary for independent variables

Independent Variables	Mean
Detailing of Medical Representative	5.60
Continues Medical Education (CME)	5.30
Medical Camps	5.95
Customer relationship management	6.27

The Mean summary statistics of 7 point likert scale questionnaire confirms the acceptance of promotional offers offered by pharmaceutical companies across the specialty categories of the sample of doctors taken in this study. The customer relationship management shows higher acceptance followed by the presence of medical camps, detailing of medical representative and continues medical education in promoting the brand and its subsequent adoption by the doctors.

Results of research hypotheses tested at significance level @5%.

Table 6: Results of structural model-research hypotheses significant at $p^{**} < 0.01$, $p^* < 0.05$

Pharmaceutical Promotional tool	Coefficient	t-Value	P-Value	Direction	Decision
Detailing of Medical Representative	0.36	4.43	0.00	Positive	Supported
Continues Medical Education	0.34	4.33	0.00	Positive	Supported
Medical Camps	0.71	4.20	0.00	Positive	Supported
Customer relationship management	0.61	7.20	0.00	Positive	Supported

The multiple linear regression model for doctor's prescription behaviour as a dependent variable using the step wise regression procedure with four independent variables resulting in a model fit measure R-Square of value 70% and all independent variables are jointly and individually affecting the study variable.

Table 7: ANOVA Table

Variable	R Square	Adjusted R Square	ANOVA
			F (p value)
Detailing of Medical Representative	0.62	0.61	64.93 (0.00)
Continues Medical Education	0.03	0.028	29.23 (0.00)
Medical Camps	0.02	0.01	16.04 (0.00)
Customer relationship management	0.73	0.71	46.42 (0.00)
Overall	0.70	0.69	35.31 (0.00)

Finally the model is tested for least square principle assumptions of error terms and the results are satisfactory as the below diagram confirm the model validity of independence between error terms and independent variables. The presence of medical camps and customer relationship management showing a positive impact in high magnitude on doctor's prescription followed by the role medical representative and continuous medical education.

Figure 3: Histogram: Significance of Prescription Behaviour

Data from the responses suggest, 65% doctors confirm that detailing of medical representative helps to recollect the brand while prescribing. 93% doctors believe that a CME with good scientific discussion with KOL can change the prescribing behaviour. 46% doctors confirms the positive impact of medical camp on their prescription. 34% doctors were neutral on the impact of medical camps on their prescription. 85% doctors feel good about customer relationship management of pharmaceutical companies. CME is the most impactful activity in attracting prescription.

The detailing of medical representative, continues medical education, prevalence of medical camps and customer relationship management are positively influencing the doctor's prescription behaviour hence all the research hypothesis are not just by chance but a positive environment created by these independent variables, therefore, all the hypothesis are accepted and supported the positive influence of the independent variables on the doctor's prescription behaviour.

DISCUSSION

Pharmaceutical marketing is more kind of personal marketing, unlike FMCG which enables pharmaceuticals to measure proper return on every promotional activity. To measure ROI of an advertisement in FMCG is not possible, whereas pharmaceuticals can measure ROI of even every visit of medical representative to doctors. The major objective of the companies is to get the maximum return on investment in terms of prescription from the invested doctors. But pharmaceutical companies are always in dilemma regarding their investments on the doctors; which investment gives maximum ROI is the major area of interest for pharmaceutical companies. The findings of this study confirmed positive correlation between the pharmaceutical promotional tactics and doctor's prescription behaviour. Better detailing and promotion in front of doctor, continues medical education, better the sampling camp / diagnostic camp at doctor's clinic & good customer relationship management support pharmaceuticals to attract the prescription support from doctors.

Detailing by Medical Sales Representative

Detailing by the medical representative (MR) is personal selling, which comes under the category of direct marketing. Medical representatives detail the brand, discuss the scientific points & resolve the doctor's query with help of visual aid to convince the doctor and start prescribing his/her brand (20). It is MRs who visit physicians to promote their company's products, through practices such as, gifting, drug detailing,

providing drug samples, sponsoring continuing medical education, conferences – all these are conveyed to the physician through the MR (21). Medical representatives are the first touch point for the pharmaceutical companies in front of doctors. MRs are the medium through companies are delivering their strategies or communication to doctors, and thereby detailing of medical representative is very crucial to pass on the proper and convincing message to doctors. As per the study, pharmaceutical companies spend almost 75% of their promotional budget on detailing (22). As per M.M. Tharaka Punchibandara et. al. factors like regular in-clinic meetings by medical representatives, discussion through scientific materials and CMEs have better impact compared to detailing and sampling (23) but majorities of prescribers expect effective communication skill and good detailing from medical representatives in order to convince for prescribing a promoted brand (24). In this era of digitalization, with e-detailing; MRs can discuss their brands more effectively in the doctor's chamber compared to traditional detailing with printed visual aids (25). The finding of this study confirms, by providing the to the point information about a brand with scientific backed up, a medical representative can convince the doctor to prescribe promoted brands. Pharmaceutical companies can invest in training of medical representative to improve their scientific & product knowledge to have better discussion with doctors, which ultimately helps doctor to recollect brand while writing prescription.

Continuing Medical Education (CME)

Continuing medical education (CME) is a platform for the medical fraternity to sharpen their competence by getting knowledge about new, upcoming and developing areas of their field. Content of CME is designed, reviewed and delivered by expert faculties of respective clinical areas. It may be either as a part of a live event or online through webcast, audio, video or other electronic media. It also can be in the form of written publications. A survey done on 150 doctors in Srilanka; confirms that continues medical education is highly impactful and positively correlated to influence doctor's prescription behaviour towards the promoted brand (23). Ahmed et al. have established a positive association between CMEs and the prescription behaviour of doctors (26). Continuing medical education that augments participant's knowledge and offers the opportunity to practice skills can change participant's prescription behaviour and, on occasion, health care outcomes (27). Traditional CMEs and passive distribution of knowledge are not effective. CMEs, which include intermittent sessions such as small group discussions or case studies, work to change medical practice and improve the quality of care. (28). The data shows the positive correlation between the continuing medical education and doctor's prescribing behaviour. Continuing medical education provides a platform for the doctors to learn about the new molecule, new usage of a drug or new indication from experts of the fraternity. Pharmaceutical companies can take mindshare of doctors by arranging CMEs for a particular brand which turns into prescription. Pharmaceuticals has also come up with the new concept in CME called webcast; whereby international or national key opinion leader (KOL) address the audience through digital media. The physical presence at CME venue is not required in webcast and participants can learn the skills from KOL at his/her place.

Medical Camps

As a part of patient care initiatives, many pharmaceutical companies organized free health check-up camps or medical camps; where they offer free diagnostic tests and trial therapy to the patients. It's a win-win situation for the doctor as well as pharmaceutical companies. Doctor gets more numbers of patients and good recognition in area nearby clinic, as well as pharmaceutical companies, get plenty of prescriptions during the camp. It's a mutual understanding between medical representatives and doctors that MR arranges camp at the doctor's clinic and in turn doctor gives a prescription of the promoted brand. Shamimulhaq et al. studied, medical camps positively impact in changing the prescription habits of medical practitioners (29). The finding supports the hypothesis of better the sampling camp / diagnostic camp at doctor's clinic, better the chance to get prescription of doctors. Medical camps with doctor help medical representative to build relationship with doctors which can be converted in to the business.

Customer relationship management

Customer relationship management (CRM) is a process where the company shapes the interactions with its customer, to maximize the lifetime value of a customer for the company, also maximize customer

satisfaction. (30). It is a new way of marketing where companies gain an understanding of how doctors perceive MRs and what factors affect those perception. If particular individualities of a MR can change these perceptions positively in the doctor's chamber; then it's crucial that companies develop those characteristics in their MRs to make them more effective in-clinic (31). Effective implementation of segmentation and targeting strategies could empower the pharmaceutical companies, to identify the proper needs of the customer which help in the right investments that results in maximum return on investment (ROI) and also increase efficiency in terms of prescription generation (30). The finding supports the positive correlation between the customer relationship management by the pharmaceutical company and its impact on doctor's prescription behaviour.

Pharmaceutical giants always try to gain the prescriptions of the doctor with their high marketing spend which ultimately increases the cost burden on the patients. Attempts have been made to control promotion through a combination of guidelines issued by Indian government and WHO, and voluntary codes adopted by industry associations and medical organizations. Various regulatory guidelines like, in 1988 the World Health Assembly framed the 'WHO Ethical Criteria for Medicinal, in 2014 the Department of Pharmaceuticals, Government of India drafted a Uniform Code for Pharmaceutical Marketing Practices (UCPMP), at the international level, the 'Code of Pharmaceutical Practices' has been developed by the International Federation of Pharmaceutical Manufacturers Associations (IFPMA), in 2009 the Medical Council India (MCI), the regulatory body for medical professionals, included in its Indian Medical Council has been developed to regulate the physician – pharmaceutical relationship (21). The Government of India tries to control such unethical practices of pharmaceutical companies by implementing The Uniform Code of Pharmaceuticals Marketing Practices (UCPMP), but the implementation of such regulation always remains a matter of concern. Generic medicines are the economical option available with patients but the reach of generic medicine stores at the rural level is very less; generic medicine options are not available for all the molecules to prescribe by a doctor and thereby patients are forced to purchase branded medicines. The quality of generic drugs is also remains a matter of concern. The government should implement stringent quality control standards on the manufacturer to provide quality generics products to the end users i.e. patients. Pharmaceutical companies find the ways and means to avoid UCPMP and try to influence doctor's prescribing behaviour, in such condition doctors need to encourage ethical medicinal practices for the wellbeing of patients.

LIMITATION & FURTHER RESEARCH

Current study focuses only on four promotional tools used by the pharmaceutical company have taken into consideration; further study requires to identify the impact of many other promotional tools like a product demonstration, sponsorship, corporate social responsibility, medical representative knowledge, leave behind literatures etc, on doctor's prescribing behaviour. Large-scale Multicentre research is needed to determine the effect of various pharmaceutical promotional tools on physician behaviour.

CONCLUSION

Every effort made by pharmaceutical companies to sell their prescription drugs plays a major role in the widespread acceptance and use of medicines in the public domain. The relationship between doctors and drug companies must be ethical and commercially competitive so that medicines reach the right place at the right time at right price. This study concludes that the role of medical representatives along with continuous medical education has a positive and significant impact on the doctor's prescription choice and at the same time the importance of customer relationship management with all the stakeholders also plays a crucial role in doctor's prescription behaviour. Government rules and regulation helps to encourage the ethical promotion of drugs by pharmaceutical companies; in India, Uniform Code of Pharmaceuticals Marketing Practices (UCPMP) is already established but the strict monitoring and implantation are required to restrict the unethical practices by means of CRM to make drugs even more economical to end-users.

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